

1. Introduction

The implementation of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change [1] prompted the rapid development of renewable energy sources in many countries. The implementation of the microgrid concept and smart grids made it possible to integrate distributed energy sources with a power from several kW to tens of MW into the central power grid [2]. For instance, quarter 2 of 2022 saw renewable electricity generation of 30.5 TWh with the total generation of 79.0 TWh in the United Kingdom. This is 12 % higher than the same period in 2021 [3]. Such processes led to a reduction in production of solid fossil fuel, in particular, hard coal. In particular, coal production in the European Union has decreased 4.8 times over the past 30 years [4]: from 277.4 Mt in 1990 to 57.2 Mt in 2021.

The closure of mines leads to the appearance of abandoned territories and dangerous locations. For instance, approximately 21 thousand mine features may pose an environmental hazard in the USA [5]. The liquidation of coal enterprises is accompanied by a number of problems: from the staff employment to ensuring the underground water balance. The last issue is especially relevant in areas with high water cut. A rise in the groundwater level in urbanized areas, where closed mines are located, can lead to land flooding, cracking of foundations, and the release of methane into the buildings basements.

The mine dewatering operation requires significant financial investments, first of all, to pay for the consumed electricity. The annual consumption can approach 4 GWh per mine for the Donetsk Basin (Ukraine) [6]. It is possible to increase the efficiency of the mine's dewatering operation by introducing a photovoltaic station (PVS). It is known about the application of PVS for a fed water pumping system with a capacity of several kW [7]. The capacity of mine pumps is several MW, so such a solution cannot be applied directly.

PVS utilization to supply mine dewatering makes it necessary to carry out bidirectional electricity metering on the low voltage side of the 110/6(10) kV transformer within the main step-down substation. The peculiarity is the significant difference in the currents flowing through the current transformers of the metering unit at the maximum output power of the PVS and in the absence of generation. Such a difference can reach two orders of magnitude, which makes it difficult to ensure the necessary accuracy of measurements. It was established in [8] that the current trans-

RESEARCH ON ACCURACY OF ELECTRICAL ENERGY MEASUREMENT IN MICROGRID FOR MINE DEWATERING

Kateryna Vasylets
PhD student

*Department of Computerized Electrotechnical Systems and Technologies
National Aviation University
1 Liubomyra Huzara ave., Kyiv, Ukraine, 03058*

Sviatoslav Vasylets

*Doctor of Technical Science, Professor¹
svyat.vasilets@gmail.com*

Anton Kylymchuk

PhD, Associate Professor¹

¹*Department of Automation, Electrical Engineering
and Computer-Integrated Technologies
National University of Water and Environmental Engineering
11 Soborna str., Rivne, Ukraine, 33028*

Abstract: The object of the study is the current transformers of the electricity metering unit as part of the microgrid for mine dewatering, which includes a photovoltaic station. The need to pump mine waters is caused by the danger of flooding large areas. The introduction of a photovoltaic station to power underground pumps reduces electricity consumption from the central power grid. At the same time, it changes the operating conditions of the metering unit. There is a need to measure both the currents of the pumps in the absence of solar generation, as well as relatively small current flows in the case of commensurate capacities generated and consumed within the microgrid. A feature of electromagnetic current transformers is a decrease in the accuracy of operation if the primary current is several percent of the rated value. Based on the analysis of variance of the experimental data, it was established that there is a statistically significant connection between the secondary and primary currents of the measuring transformer at insignificant values of the primary current. Estimates of the values of the linear regression parameters that link the secondary and primary currents were determined. It was established that in the range of the transformer primary current from 0.22 % to 1.4 %, the current error reaches a value of 6.7 %. Taking into account the resulting dependence in the software of the electricity metering unit will make it possible to increase the accuracy of energy metering. Accordingly, the accuracy of financial calculations will be increased.

Keywords: photovoltaic station, water pump, current transformer, error, regression line, metering unit.

formers characteristics have a decisive influence on the static conversion function of the measuring channel of the metering unit. In this work, such characteristics at reduced primary current were not determined. The need to ensure correct financial calculations between the energy supply company and the mine, when implementing a microgrid for dewatering, determines the relevance of the revealed scientific issue.

The aim of research is to improve the accuracy of electricity metering in microgrid, equipped with photovoltaic station, for mine dewatering by evaluating characteristic of measuring current transformer at reduced primary current. This will make it possible to increase the accuracy of calculations with the power supply company in conditions of random PVS output power.

To achieve the aim, the following tasks must be solved:

- to perform analysis of variance of experimental data obtained in laboratory, which describes the functioning of measuring current transformers at reduced primary current;

- to estimate the value of the regression line parameters, which corresponds to the dependence between secondary and primary currents, when the values of the primary current do not exceed a few percent of the rated value.

2. Methods

The object of the study is the current transformers of the electricity metering unit as part of the microgrid for mine dewatering, which includes a photovoltaic station.

The metering unit includes the electricity meter PIK₁, which is connected using current transformers TA₁–TA₃ and provides accounting of power flows between the microgrid and the external power grid PG, Fig. 1. A PVS, consisting of multi-string inverters Inv₁–Inv_n with several maximum power point trackers MPPT, is connected to the 6(10) kV buses of the main step-down substation using a TV2 power transformer. A string of serially connected photovoltaic modules (N_{ms}) is connected to the input of MPPT. PV array includes N_{mp} of such string. The mine dewatering pumps, located at the depth H_s in the mine shaft yard, are driven by induction motors M₁–M_k. The latter are supplied through the trunk cable from the 6(10) kV buses of the main step-down substation.

Research is carried out for the conditions considered in the paper [6]. The operation of PVS with the optimal rated capacity of 3.1640 MW for Bilytska Mine (Donetsk region, Ukraine) is analyzed. The active power of two pumping units of the dewatering system, which working simultaneously, is 1.7320 MW. For such a

4. Discussion

As a result of analysis of variance, it was statistically confirmed that there is a relationship between the primary and secondary currents of the measuring transformer in the range of $I_p^* < 1.4\%$. Regression analysis made it possible to establish that the dependence of the secondary current of measuring transformers on the relative value of the primary current (from 0.22% to 1.4%) is linear and is described by equation (1). At the point of the smallest load $I_p^* = 0.22\%$, the value of the secondary current calculated according to dependence (1) is $I_s = 10.265$ mA, which in relative units $I_s^* = 0.205\%$. In this case, the current error is -6.7% . At the point $I_p^* = 1.4\%$ according to (1) the secondary current is $I_s = 68.723$ mA, $I_s^* = 1.374\%$, and the current error is -1.9% .

The advantage of this study, compared to [6], is the derivation of expression (1) for the static characteristics of current transformers in the area of low primary currents. Taking into account the obtained dependence in the software of the electricity metering unit will make it possible to increase the accuracy of the metering of energy flows between the microgrid and the power grid. Accordingly, the accuracy of financial calculations will be increased. The limitations of the study include obtaining results only for two types of low-voltage transformers (300/5 and 600/5). The disadvantage of dependence (1) is its deterministic nature. The estimation of confidence intervals would make it possible to assess the accuracy of the measurement from a statistical point of view. In the course of further research, it is advisable to clarify the hourly power flows between the microgrid and the power grid and the corresponding current measurement errors.

5. Conclusions

Analysis of variance of empirical data confirmed the existence of a statistically significant relationship between the secondary and the primary currents of the measuring transformer as part of the metering unit at insignificant values of the primary current. This confirms the possibility of increasing the accuracy of electricity metering in the microgrid for mine dewatering during close values of power consumed by pumping units and generated by a photovoltaic station.

Estimates of the parameters values of the linear regression connecting the secondary and primary currents of the measuring transformers were established. Taking into account the resulting dependence in the software of the metering unit will improve the accuracy of electricity accounting. The necessity of such a correction is confirmed by a significant current error, which can reach 6.7%.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Availability of data

The manuscript has no associated data.

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